

Prototyping and control of a 3D printed bionic hand operated by myoelectric signals: toward accessibility for amputees

Carlos Eduardo Pontim
Faculdade de Engenharia Mecatrônica
Centro Universitário de Maringá
Maringá, Brazil
 ORCID: 0000-0001-9113-3754

Daniel Prado Campos
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do
Paraná (UTFPR)
Curitiba – PR
 ORCID 0000-0001-6233-6077

Mariza Akiko Utida
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Instituto Federal do Parana (IFPR)
Maringa, Brazil
 ORCID: 0000-0002-0725-8747

Joao Antônio Palma Setti
Doutorado - Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do
Paraná (UTFPR)
Curitiba, Brazil
 ORCID 0000-0003-0659-1297

Abstract—The present work shows the development of a low-cost bionic hand, which purpose is to restore life quality, improve self-esteem and ease of acquisition for people who had their hands amputated from illnesses or accidents. The prosthesis was designed for transradial amputations, that is, below the elbow, having all its modeling made by CAD software. In the development of the bionic hand, the focus was the realization of three main movements: flexion and extension of the fingers and pinch. For the prototyping of the prosthesis a 3D printer of own construction was used. The Bionic Hand is controlled by surface electromyographic (sEMG) signal, derived from muscle contraction. The model chosen to control the robotic hand is based on the ATmega328P microcontroller and a Myo Armband bracelet, used for the acquisition of myoelectric signals and gesture recognition.

Keywords—Prosthesis; 3D Printer; Modeling; Myoelectric Prosthesis; Bionic Hand; sEMG

I. INTRODUCTION

The loss of a limb can be resulted from a congenital deficiency caused by genetic variation or an acquired deficiency. Also, by function of diabetes, peripheral vascular disease, trauma and malignancy. The person undergoes sudden changes in their lives, affecting his/her behavior and especially psychological, resulting problems of depression or anxiety due to amputation. The transformations occurring in individuals are perceived at a global level insofar as individuals see themselves in some way less independent; cause or increasing the difficulties that will be proportional to their limitations [2].

The myoelectric signal is known as EMG, which consists of an electrical potential generated according to the contraction of the muscle. Moreover, it can be captured through a sensor on the skin surface (sEMG) [4].

A prosthesis is a device that replaces a missing part of the body, and it is technically a complete item. The complete prosthesis would consist of the residual limb fixation system (usually a "socket") and all fixation hardware components, including the terminal device [3].

The world-wide prosthetics market offers several state-of-the-art models with a variety of features, however because it is not yet produced on a large scale and has high technology

components it is usually expensive. For example, the Ottobock Bebionic V3 device, created from aluminum alloy has 14 different patterns of footprint and hand positions with power control made by carbon fiber. It weighs about 600 grams and costs up to \$ 25,000 [6]. Therefore it does not reach large numbers of people who need their use.

The 3D printing is called rapid prototyping, where a part is created from a 3D drawing. It is possible to get physical model from virtual 3D data rapidly. Besides, it has the prosthetic technology standardised procedures with long history. This type of process of an object is quicker and economically more accessible. Nowadays, there are fortunately a great number of so-called open technologies. One of such very well-known unpatented technique is for instance FFF (Fused Filament Fabrication). It is equivalent technology to FDM (Fused Deposition Modelling) which is already not patented but the FDM is registered trademark of Stratasys company [5].

Both technologies work with thermoplastic polymers. In recent years, a 3D printer has demonstrated a new way of thinking about making prostheses. The use has allowed extremely customizable designs taking into account the circumstances of each individual, which leads to a better device and thus higher quality of life and rehabilitation [1].

This work presents a myoelectric bionic hand controlled from the activation of muscular stimuli, using components and devices available in the market, with relatively low cost. A 3D printer was developed for structural construction and confections of the mechanical parts, being able to reduce not only the development cost, but also the time of design and manufacture, besides being light, resistant and functional.

The prosthesis was integrated with a controller implemented by an Arduino UNO with a serial communication based on myoelectric signals collected from the Myo Armband bracelet. This system can collect eight sEMG channels that are processed and classified, providing as output the movements for the prosthetic device. Six mini direct current motors with gear reduction was used to coordinate the prosthesis movements, being a motor used for each finger and two for the thumb, improving the prosthesis movements.

II. DEVELOPMENT

A. 3D model of prosthesis

Current prosthetics found on the market are approaching a human hand for its movement capabilities and appearance. Although there are a variety of products, the processes and modeling required make the final product values high. The main goal of this project is to provide a highly functional low-cost prosthetic hand for people with below the elbow amputations. The modeling was based on the Open Source project Bretl Research Group [7], in order to bring an active prosthetic device controlled by sEMG sensors that focuses on the movement of extension, flexion, and pincer movement. Therefore, giving the possibility to restore the amputee's self-esteem.

Fig. 1 Bionic hand: Physical dimensions of the prosthesis.

B. Structural and electrical development

After developing the modeling, the artificial hand components were 3D printed. This method was chosen for its rapid prototyping and precision, producing something realistic and detailed of the modeled design, having low price of printing and suitable pieces mechanical resistance.

The printer used in the work was a 3D printer of its own construction (Fig. 2), model Graber, with a model Bowden workspace of 220x220x205 mm. The impression of the prosthesis went through two versions. In the first version, the material used to print it was PLA (Polylactic acid) and in the second ABS (Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene) was used.

Fig. 2: 3D printer engraver model, own creation, developed to make the pieces of the prosthesis

It was observed that the PLA version did not present adequate resistance for the determined purpose. For the second version all parts were rebuilt in ABS, where it provided improvement in resistance. In the printing process, an Open-Source slicing software called Repetier-Host was used. The software is compatible with most firmware and can build the STL (Standard Template Library).

The impression of the prosthesis totaled in 26:20 hours, using around 70 meters of filament, corresponding to 210 g of filament according to the 3D Printing software.

Artificial limbs active by external force do not produce the desired movement of the given function, requiring a mechanical transformation to the transmission mechanisms. Coupled to the motor system, they also have several possible configurations, and the correct choice of mechanism becomes essential for prosthesis efficiency. In this project, the mini motors with reduction were chosen (Fig. 3) using six motors in total, one for each finger and two for the thumb.

The articulated systems are composed of a system of levers and joints in order to reproduce the movements of the human hand, denominated as tensors, which are coupled between the proximal and the distal locations of the hand, facilitating the control of the finger movements. A crown and endless gear were also developed using 3D Printing, used to couple the DC motors and the finger movements.

Fig. 3 Interior of the prosthesis: a) motors and gears; b) Interior of the Prosthesis.

In order to make the prototype accessible, the forearm prosthesis was not included in the project. Therefore, because it is not an end product, it was necessary to develop a base to accommodate the hand and the electric components that drive it for aesthetics purpose. The internal part of the base was made hollow with enough space for the fixation of all the electrical components, offering protection to the mechanical shocks and aiding in the transport of the project.

C. Control

The control system discussed in this work is an open-loop system, having as input the signals obtained by the Myo Armband bracelet, which acquire the myographic signals from the muscles. The Arduino microcontroller in serial connection with the Myduino application performs the signal processing, where its outputs are the DC motors.

Therefore, the prosthesis is controlled by surface electromyography (sEMG) signal, derived from muscle

contraction. Thus, the model chosen to control the robotic hand is based on the ATmega328P microcontroller, Arduino Uno. In order to capture the sEMG signals, the Myo Armband bracelet, developed by Thamil Labs, was chosen. This device is an 8-channel wireless electromyograph with an inertial sensor which acquires signals from the musculature and movements of the forearm.

The firmware of the prosthesis was developed in the Arduino IDE, in C language and consists in recognizing which gesture is executed and converts it into specific commands for the hand motors. The communication between Arduino and the Myo Armband is done through the MyoDuino application, which sends the performed gesture information to Arduino, where it receives and processes this information through the MyoController library.

Fig. 4: Serial communication flowchart.

Initially, the Myo library is defined (MyoController.h), after that the outputs are determined, where each identified hand movement is associated with a set of motor commands. For example, by performing the hand-closing movement, the prosthesis will consecutively drive the motors to close the fingers.

Table I. Commands and Functions

COMMANDS	FUNCTIONS
<i>Fist</i>	Close
<i>Spread Fingers</i>	Open
<i>Wave in</i>	Pincer movement
<i>Wave Out</i>	Undo Pincer movement
<i>Double Tap</i>	Lock / Unlock

In order to control the DC motors, a driver was required to reverse the direction of rotation of the motor, being the L293D chosen for the task. This electronic device is an integrated circuit that contains two complete H-bridges (or four half H-bridges). With it, it is possible to control two DC motors bidirectionally. It took two external batteries to power the L293D, which power DC motors and capacitors which were employed as analogical filters.

Fig. 5 Electrical diagram of the prosthesis.

III. RESULTS

For the analysis of the sEMG signals acquired by the armband, using the following protocol: each movement was performed during 5 seconds followed by 5 seconds of rest. The movements were: Fist, spread fingers, wave in, wave out and double touch. Figures 6 shows example of each movement signal (8-channels).

Fig. 6 Types of movements and their signals: Fist(Grey); Spread Fingers(Green); Wave in(Blue); Wave out(Purple); Double tap(Yellow).

The electromyographic signals were classified using the armband framework itself, which classifies movements from 8-channel EMG signals with a sampling frequency of 200 Hz with 8-bit resolution. The framework provided by Myo (Thalnic labs) presents an encapsulated feature extractor and classifier, so future works, already under development, involve obtaining the raw signals from Myo and performing the entire processing chain (segmentation, feature extraction and classification).

The figure 7 shows the three movements of the prosthesis: extension, flexion and pincer movement.

Fig. 7 Positions obtained by the prosthesis compared to a human hand: a) Open; b) Close; c) Pincer movement;

IV. CONCLUSION

Due to the mentioned facts, this paper has shown that the inclusion of 3D printer is possible develop custom prostheses. In fact it was not optimized for an individual, however it is possible to customize the models are available. Therefore, the prostheses can restore the quality of life of a person who had an amputation on the forearm, however it was not evaluated, is a hypothesis to be tested in future works. The employment of the 3D printer resulted in the immediate feedback of the printed parts, facilitating in the prototyping and resulting a low cost of production. The ABS filament presented better resistance, improving the mechanisms fittings, having a light weight for the prosthesis, weighing 276 g (520 g when with the base).

The Prosthesis presented a good rightful control of the bionic hand, however the complete movement period interval lasts around 3 seconds. Another limitation concerning the final system is that the lack of feedback and other type of sensors in the bionic hand may result in uncontrolled movements, tight grip or excessive hyperflexion. To overpass this issue a sensorless angle control must be implemented in future development.

As for the cost analysis, the developed prosthesis was optimized to minimize costs when compared to other prostheses that also use the myoelectric control. Having a 3D printer and a computer, the values of the components, filament and the bracelet resulted in a value of R\$ 975.00 Reais (Brazilian currency) according to Table 2.

Table II. Cost table

AMOUNT	COMPONENTS	VALUES (R\$)
6	MOTORS	190,00
1	ARDUINO	35,00
1	PROTOBOARD	20,00
3	L293D (PONTE H)	20,00
1	MYO ARMBAND	550,00
1KG	FILAMENT ABS	80,00
2	BATTERIES 9V	40,00
10	CAPACITORS 0,1UF	4,00
3	CAPACITORS 100UF/50V	6,00
1M	LINEAR GUIDE 3MM	10,00
1M	LINEAR GUIDE 4MM	14,00
2M	PARALLEL CABLE 1,5MM	6,00
TOTAL		975,00

Regarding the bionic hand, its physical characteristics presented robustness and an innovative design. Another positive point in the modeling was the question of the movement and articulation of the fingers, chosen by a system composed of levers and joints that originated movements proposed in the work. The development of gears provided smooth and even transmission movements, but the fact that this components were 3D Printed caused torque limitation. It is suggested that gears and transmission parts should be build out of metallic or more resistant materials.

Regarding the control part, the communication between the Arduino and the Myo bracelet showed that it was possible to perform the positions of the prosthesis. The tests were performed in their own authors, with the bracelet connected to the right arm, performing the movements, the prosthesis responded to the programmed stimuli, as shown in figure 7.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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